

BRANCHES OF UZBEK LEXICOLOGY IN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: Lexicology is considered main and fundamental branch of linguistics. Its role in modern science and interrelation with other field is thoroughly analyzed. In this article theoretical foundations of lexicology's components (lexicography, phraseology, semasiology, semantics, etymology, stylistics) are highlighted. The author focuses on the nature and structure of the word, emphasizing it as an integral part of a linguistic system rather than an isolated unit.

Key words: Lexicology, language, linguistics, linguistic system, lexicography, phraseology, semasiology, semantics, etymology, stylistics, nature of the word, lexis, historical evolution, Uzbek lexicology, grammar, communication, lexicon, human cognition, systemic interrelation, synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, paronyms, phonetics, dialect, terminology.

Language – is a sophisticated, social, systemic process that consists of specific components (sound, word, sentence), and the means of communication, changing information and thinking. It is learned as a product of activity (speech) and synchronic and diachronic system in historical development. Human cognition's formation and manifestation realizes in language. It lives and develops with society, and it is common to the members of the community. Language is dynamic system that always in process and changes. Linguistics study language not only as a means of communication, but also as a system based on rules and regulations (grammar, lexicon and phonetics).

Language consists of different levels and components. One of these components is **lexicology** (in Greek *lexicos* – so'zga oid, *logos* – o'qitmoq), which studies the vocabulary of a language. It studies words' meaning, origin, usage and systemic interrelations. Lexicology is the main space to understand language's lexical richness. The main studying object of lexicology is “the word”.

Meaning of words (semasiology): The concept a word expresses. For example, the fruit that comes to mind when we say “olma”. In this area literal and figurative meanings (metaphor, metonymy) are studied here. Words may be with one or several meanings. If the word is used in several meanings it is called Polysemy. For example, “bosh” means -body part, director, introduction at the same time. When the word has a single meaning it is called Monosemy. For instance, scientific terms have single meaning usually.

Lexical microsystems: Words' synonymous relations:

Synonyms: Words with similar meanings (chiroyli, go'zal, latofatli).

Antonyms: Words with opposite meanings (oq-qora, katta-kichik).

Homonyms: Words with same form but different meanings (kir- sifat, kir-harakat).

Paronyms: Words with similar pronunciation but different meanings (adab-odob, shoh-shox).

Lexicology consists of several branches, each branch studies different aspects of lexical richness of language.

1. Semasiology is a branch of lexicology that studies meanings of words. It examines how words express different meanings and how these meanings are formed and changed in language. Semasiology is mainly concerned with the relationship between words and the concepts they represent.

In language, words can have both literal and figurative meanings. Moreover, such occurrences as metaphor and metonymy are studied here. A metaphor is based on similarity between two things. For example, “*oltin qo'l*” means a very skillful person. A metonymy is based on association or connection. For example, “*The White House*” means the government, not the building. These processes show how word meanings develop on language.

2. Onomasiology studies how concepts are named in language. This branch focuses on the process of naming and how people choose words to name objects, actions, and concepts in communication.

For example, the concept of a place where people live can be expressed in different ways such as “*uy*”, “*xonadon*”, “*maskan*” or “*qarorgoh*” in Uzbek language. The word “*uy*” is more general and commonly used in everyday speech, while “*xonadon*” is more formal.

Onomasiology helps us understand how people choose words to express their thoughts and how language reflects human cognition.

3. Etymology studies origin and historical development of words. It explains where words come from, how they have changed in form and meaning, and how they entered a language over time. For example, the word “*etimologiya*” itself comes from Greek: “*lexicos*” meaning “*so'zga oid*” and “*logos*” meaning “*o'qimoq*” or “*o'qitmoq*”. This shows that etymology is closely connected with the history of language.

Many words in modern languages have different origins. Some words are borrowed from other languages, while others are native. For instance, the word “*kitob*” and “*maktab*” have different historical roots. The word “*telefon*” comes from Greek where “*tele*” means “*uzoq*” and “*phone*” means “*tovush*”.

Etymology also helps us understand cultural and historical connections between different nations. In addition, etymology makes it easier to understand and remember vocabulary.

4. Phraseology studies fixed expressions and idiomatic phrases in a language. These expressions are called phraseological units or idioms, and they have a stable structure and a single meaning. The meaning of phraseological units cannot be understood by translating each word separately.

Phraseological units play an important role in making speech more expressive, emotional, and colorful. They are widely used in spoken, written language, especially in literature and everyday communication.

For example, in Uzbek language, expressions like “*ko'z ochib yumguncha*” (very quickly), “*tili uzun*” (a person who talks too much) have figurative meanings. These expressions do not reflect their literal meanings, but rather convey a different idea as a whole.

Phraseological units are important for language learning, as they help learners sound more natural and fluent.

5. Lexicography deals with dictionary compilation. It studies how words are collected, described, and organized in dictionaries. Lexicography plays an important role in systemizing the vocabulary of a language.

There are two main aspects of lexicography: theoretical and practical. Theoretical lexicography focuses on the principles of dictionary-making, such as how to define words, how to classify meanings, and how to present information clearly. Practical lexicography, on the other hand, is concerned with the actual creation of dictionaries.

In Uzbek language, dictionaries like “*O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati*” play an important role in preserving and developing the language. They help users understand word meanings, correct spelling, pronunciation, and usage.

6. Terminology studies special words or terms used in different fields of science, technology, and professional activity. Terms are words or expressions that have a clear and precise meaning within a particular subject area.

For example, in medicine we use words like diagnosis, treatment, virus; in computer science we use software, hardware, internet. These terms help specialists communicate accurately and avoid misunderstanding. One of the main features of terms is that they are usually monosemantic, meaning they have only one specific meaning.

Terminology is important for scientific development because it ensures clarity and precision in communication. It also helps students and professionals understand and use the language of their field correctly.

7. Onomastics studies proper names. It includes the study of personal names, place names, names of rivers, mountains, and other geographical objects.

Onomastics is usually divided into several subfields. Anthroponymy studies personal names, while toponymy studies place names. These areas help researchers understand the history and culture of a people.

Studying onomastics allows us to see how language is connected with identity and tradition, and how names are used to represent individuals and places.

8. Dialectology studies regional varieties of a language, known as dialects. It examines differences in pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar in different regions.

In every language, people living in different areas may use different words for the same concept. For example, in Uzbek, some words may vary from one region to another. These differences show the richness and diversity of the language.

Understanding dialects is important for linguists, as it provides information about the history and development of a language.

In conclusion, lexicology is an important branch of linguistics that studies the vocabulary of a language, including the meaning, origin, and usage of words. Its main branches, such as semasiology, onomasiology, etymology, and others, help us understand how words function and develop in language.

Moreover, studying lexicology improves our vocabulary and communication skills. It also helps us use language more accurately and understand the connection between language, culture, and human thinking.

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